

Scientific Study on the Institution of Marriage within the Framework of the Turkish Civil Code No. 4721

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The family is an essential institution in Turkish culture and tradition. Its primary goals are to ensure the continuity of the human race from one generation to the next and to foster the development of physically and mentally sound offspring. On the other hand, as a result of shifts in both legal and religious standards, there are now certain marriages that are not entered into with the intention of bearing children. This is particularly true in monogamous marriages and marriages between blood relatives. According to Article 4721 of the Turkish Civil Code, "marriage" is defined as a social and spiritual institution that is formed when two individuals of opposite sexes join together to create a complete and long-lasting living union.

Limitations

The limitations of the research are limited to the extent of the subject in the world literature and data. Research is restricted to closely related researchers and literature. It is also limited to literature survey.

Notices

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Ethical Declaration

Publishing ethics of the relevant regulations of our university; It is a national-based scientific study that aims to ensure that scientific research and publications are made in accordance with basic principles such as honesty, openness, objectivity, respect for the findings and creations of others, and aims to realize these principles in the field of related disciplines.

Abstract

The family is an essential institution in Turkish culture and tradition. Its primary goals are to ensure the continuity of the human race from one generation to the next and to foster the development of physically and mentally sound offspring. On the other hand, as a result of shifts in both legal and religious standards, there are now certain marriages that are not entered into with the intention of bearing children. This is particularly true in monogamous marriages and marriages between blood relatives. According to Article 4721 of the Turkish Civil Code, "marriage" is defined as a social and spiritual institution that is formed when two individuals of opposite sexes join together to create a complete and long-lasting living union. It is subject to monogamous principles that ban both men and women from marrying more than one person. The state guarantees marriage, but with constraints; marriage is subject to these monogamous rules. This is accomplished via the use of a family law contract, and since people of both sexes may agree on their understanding of what marriage entails, a marriage contract can be finalized. Those who want to be married have to do so in the presence of the person who will perform the ceremony, and they have to make sure that the wording of their declarations is articulated very specifically and orally. Even if neither party makes a remark verbally and instead only signs the marriage book, this does not render the contract for the marriage null and void. In accordance with the provisions of Article 141 of the Turkish Civil Code, there must be a minimum of two witnesses present at the same moment. The marriage is considered "absent" if it is determined that the declaration of the man and woman to marry is not conducted in a suitable manner. However, giving up on the idea of getting married does not count

toward this component in any way, shape, or form, nor does the transfer of any property or monetary assets. This study sheds light on the requirements for getting married as well as the possible difficulties that may present themselves after these requirements have been satisfied. The constitutional protection of the notion of family, which was established after the establishment of the institution, may be found in Article 41 of the Turkish Constitution. In the course of the investigation, it will also be important to the formal and substantive requirements that need to be satisfied for a marriage to be discussed as legitimate, as well as the rulings that the Supreme Court has rendered about this topic.

Keywords: Marriage, Condition, Validity in Marriage, Invalidity, Obstacle in Marriage

Introduction

If the man and woman who are seeking marriage show up before the marriage official at separate times or if one of the couples is replaced by their legal counsel, it will be difficult for the marriage to go through. This topic is connected to the lack of marriage in a Supreme Court ruling. Each person is asked to be married by the marriage officer, and they must respond verbally in the affirmative. The signing of the minutes by a third party during the marriage ceremony is an illustration of how a marriage cannot be done by proxy. According to the legal theory advanced in the courts and largely agreed upon by French attorneys, marriage's legal requirements need to be regarded as a contract. The supporters in these discussions contend that marriage is seen as an institution rather than a transaction. Arguments that marriage's terms and conditions, seen as a contract, may be simply controlled are only natural.

From the moment the parties' marriages accumulate

The laws control the terms to which the marriage will be subject and the circumstances for the dissolution of the marriage for people who are significant in terms of marriage and who declare their desire exclusively to proceed down the path of marriage. The terms of the contract will no longer be contingent on the wishes of the married persons the minute the parties dissolve their marriage. This conclusion does not take into account the lack of the "free will" principle, which has the authority to govern the parties' legal relationships in accordance with their own preferences.

Legal Limits of Marriage in Turkey

The legal restrictions on marriage in Turkey are approached from many different angles, making them complicated and varied. The general consensus is that marriage is a "Civil Law Contract" with predetermined terms. The terms "Marriage Law" and "Barriers to Marriage License" are used to describe this circumstance. The Civil Code provides rules on the material connections of the building of their house, including the "Marriage Law" and "Barriers to Marriage License" sections. Being of sound mind, having attained the age of marriage, and not being prohibited from contacting a legal authority are only a few of the requirements for being married under Civil Law. Those with the capacity to freely decide and act are those who already possess the capability of discernment. A person who lacks the legal right to discriminate entails the legal invalidity of a contract, such a user marriage contract. According to Article 13 of the Civil Code, it is necessary to have the ability to discern between those who are not incapable of having a center of action owing to old age, mental disease, mental weakness, or intoxication. This authorization is not restricted to people with healthy structures, no mental impairments, or those in dire circumstances like a youngster with a mental disease or a person who has been arrested for drug usage. The lawmaker understood that every adult has the capacity to reason, and that age plays a significant role in an individual's mental stability and growth throughout time.

It is a psychological idea that may lead to discrimination and can be broken down into categories like mental illness, psychosis, mania, schizophrenia, paranoia, organic storytelling, epilepsy, hysteria, and mental disintegration. Psychosis, mania, schizophrenia, paranoia, different sorts of organic storytelling, epilepsy, hysteria, and mental depression are among the sub- and specific categories that may be used to further categorize distinguishing mental deaths. Temporary inability to discriminate at regular intervals is brought up by temporary weakness, apologies, and a lack of comprehension of punishment.

The mental hospital isn't a good enough excuse to get rid of usage management since it's a proven marital obstacle. Mental weakness is one of the causes of this. Because people who lack fully developed brains and the ability to act also lack the ability to

reason. Mental weakness should not be seen as an illness but rather as a lack of mental imagination or a progressive deterioration of mental abilities rather than as a disease.

Drunkenness at the time of marriage is an issue that has to be addressed, according to Article 13 of the Turkish Civil Code. For instance, it is evident that negative marriage relationship effects brought on by alcohol momentarily impair one's thinking and purpose and result in unconsciousness. When using alcohol, the impact it has on the individual should be prioritized above the kind or quantity. It is sufficient to show someone is not an alcoholic by witness evidence. Marriage maturity is defined as being older than the legal marriage age at which a woman and a man should enter into a marriage contract.

Determining the Age of Marriage as the Lower Limit

Setting a minimum age for marriage compels people to mature to a particular extent, which is typical for children and necessary for progress. The majority of international legal weddings set a lower marriage age and stipulate that the union cannot happen until the pair achieves that age.

Setting an upper age restriction for marriage is not a crucial decision since it is handled by the natural laws. During childhood, fewer couples marry each other. The lower age restriction for marriage has been established by the Turkish Legislator, but the higher age limit has not yet been defined. In accordance with Article 124 of the Turkish Civil Code, a person cannot get married until they are seventeen years old. The first day of the month is used as a foundation if the month and year are listed on the identification card. Article 124 of the Turkish Civil Code specifies a reduced age restriction for both men and women to wed. For males and women, various age ranges were established under the previous Civil Code. Both the guy and the bride must be at least 17 years old. The lower age restriction (18 years) for divorced marriage has been established by the lawmaker. In a similar vein, the Civil Code continues to regulate marriage age in a manner that is consistent with general maturity. There has been much debate regarding setting the marriageable age based on a shorter life than the average puberty. In terms of the parties to the marriage contract before the age of majority, it is described as the person's incapacity to act legally or to sign a contract, that is, not having full

capacity. The legislature, however, mandates the power to establish the age of marriage as a lower age in comparison to the age of majority, taking into consideration the circumstances and necessities of the time. The legislator makes plans in accordance with the time's rules and regulations. Some international laws set the usual marriage age before the person reaches adulthood. Some nations' civil codes set different marriage ages for men and women. age at marriage varies per nation:

- *Germany, 18 for men and women;*
- *France, 18 for men and 15 for women;*
- *Denmark is 20 for the early age and 18 for the female;*
- *Sweden is 18 for men and women;*
- *Austria, 21 for the early age and 16 for the female;*
- *Greece, 18 for the early age and 14 for the female;*
- *Italy, age 16 for men and 14 for women.*

In 1926, the legal age of marriage was changed to be 18 for males and 17 for women. The lawmakers authorized these rules by adjusting them in accordance with their laws, since the Swedish Civil Code stipulates that men and women must be 20 and 18 respectively before they may be married. However, owing to the popularity of early marriage, certain amendments have been made to Article 88's stated marriage age. The marriage letter was reorganized in 1938 and modified to 17 for males and 15 for women with the passing of statute number 3543. The Civil Code has undergone its first revision with this one.

Methodology

Early marriage has several disadvantages, particularly for women. For instance, housekeeping has long-lasting psychological effects on young ladies who marry young. A woman has to be mentally ready before she can be a mother. Preterm birth rates are greater among moms under the age of 18. The usual marriage age in Turkey is 17 years old for both men and women, as stated in article 124/I of the Turkish Civil Code. It is necessary to concentrate on reducing or raising the typical marriage age in comparison to the time given the circumstances of today. "Judicial marriage maturity"

or "marriage age" refers to the minimum and maximum ages at which individuals who have not yet achieved marriageable age may legally wed under certain circumstances.

Legal marriage refers to a maturity notion akin to the "maturity" governed by Article 12 of the Civil Code. Men and women who are determined to be of legal age by a court order do not reach the traditional age of marriage concurrently with this judgment. A person above the age of 15, who the court has determined to be of legal age, is unable to be married since he or she has not yet turned 17 years old. The lady and the husband must be at least 17 years old or comply with Civil Code 124/II in order to get married. They had to have gotten a marriage license from the court in accordance with the provisions of their agreement.

Judges may wed an adult if there is a very good cause, according to Turkish Civil Code Article 4 of the Turkish Civil Code. The court must investigate the incident and gather evidence to identify the cause. However, breaking this rule is against both the law and the protocol. Other significant factors are parental support, the prospect of moving to a foreign country with lower marriage ages, death threats or mistreated women. The Supreme Court also takes into account significant factors including living as husband and wife, sharing a home, and being under guardianship.

In conclusion, the court's discretion to approve a marriage relies on the significance of the situation and the justification. Court rulings in Turkey have a significant impact on the legal status of juveniles because of the challenges associated with their temporary status. Penalties also apply to adolescents who are denied legal rights to marriage, such as inheritance rights and divorce compensation. While some courts consider the fact that a couple is living together as husband and wife to be a significant factor, others do not.

Argument

According to Civil Code regulations, the court must, wherever feasible, give preference to the woman's parents or guardians and her husband before marriage. To improve the situation, a new version of this clause has been added. In certain situations, the court may approve the union of the pair without the agreement of the parents or

guardians, or even with their consent, even though neither the woman nor the man stands to gain from the union. The Family Court has the responsibility of securing a marriage license, and it is able to visit the couple's home if they want to do so. It is possible for marriage permits to be used in discriminatory ways. The Public Prosecutor's Office proved the total nullity of a marriage that was entered into without the judge's consent, but the Court of Cassation overruled the counterarguments and claims against it because of the age of the local court.

who are fully capable of entering into marriage without need the assistance of anybody. For persons who are handicapped or have poor judgment, there are certain requirements for marriage. Minors cannot marry themselves because they are underage, even if they reach the legal marriage age. The same holds true for older minors. People with limited ability are those chosen by law to serve as representatives. If there isn't a compelling cause to limit them yet their interests require that they do so, an explanation is required. People who aren't mature enough to marry, who can't discriminate between right and wrong, and who haven't attained marriageable age are utterly incapable of being married. With the permission of the court or their legal agent, these people cannot get married. There are two types of marital restrictions: those that are legally specified and those that are not.

Consanguinity, current marriages, and mental instability are all undeniable obstacles to getting married. Due to the potential health risks to the unborn child, Article 129 of the Civil Code forbids marriage between a man and a woman who are related to one another. Additionally, it is crucial that those who make decisions and the institutions or courts that approve marriages assess the moral standards of the union of men and women with familial links.

As a consequence, the legal status of their young child and any future marriage in Turkey are greatly influenced by court rulings. The total influence of marriage on the lives and financial rights of Europeans remains a complicated topic, even though some courts believe these components to be significant.

Marriage Principles After Adoption Date

The ideas of marriage after the date of adoption have been a part of Turkish Civil Code for a very long time. The new rule only permits one marriage, as opposed to the previous Civil Code's multiple marriage allowance. The idea behind this alteration, known as polygamy, is that the kinship does not cease with the dissolution of the preexisting structure.

Religious weddings are not seen as a barrier to marriage, while civil marriage confirms the idea of marriage with a single individual. However, even if the first marriage ends in divorce or death, the individual may be married again. A person having a religious marriage may legally wed another person, and the idea of marriage with one person is legitimate for formal weddings.

One of the married spouses may get involved in polygamy as a consequence of their union, which is against Turkish Civil Code and is deemed to be an absolute nullity. The marriage time ends and the departed person's qualities vanish at the death of one of the married men or women. When a spouse dies during a marriage, the surviving spouse, or the status of the marriage, there is no need to go back to court. Even if the surviving spouse is free to wed another person after passing away, the in-law connection endures. According to 129b, the surviving spouse cannot wed the parent or descendant of the dead spouse, and the spouse of the deceased cannot wed those who are prohibited from wedlock.² While the existing marriage is not ended by the union's absence, it is now essential to file for the dissolution of the marriage. The surviving spouse continues the existing marriage only if he has chosen to be absent and has not filed any paperwork seeking the annulment of the marriage. If the marriage is broken due to the absence of the union, a re-marriage contract should be made in the event that the non-existence of the union occurs.

Persons Confirmed Death

Article 31 of the Civil Code states that even if a person's body isn't discovered, they are still regarded as certain mortals. The population registry for the individual contains the death notice and the information that the death has passed. The marriage should be void if it happens again after he passes away in the civil register if the surviving spouse marries as a consequence of this circumstance. In this instance, one of the reasons for

dissolving a marriage is the death of one of the partners. This condition remains unchanged notwithstanding the death announcement in the population registry. Following the finalization of the divorce judgment, each divorced individual may remarry or remarry their ex-spouse. According to MK. Article 133, a mental test and a report from an official health facility that is not sensitive to their marriage must be in agreement before they may be married. Although not all mental disorders are covered by this rule, it does mention that mental illness typically interferes with marriage. The pair will not be prevented from getting married if it is shown by a certified health institution report that the individual's current mental condition will not result in any defects in terms of marriage. This strategy safeguards the marriage of those who are mentally ill. Article 89 of the Former Civil Code makes it clear that it seeks to do away with justification and recognizes any mental institution as an absolute ban and marriage prohibition.

But according to the measurements, there is no longer any prejudice towards those with mental illnesses. The major aim is to maintain the objectives and continuity of the generation, accepting the principles of reason as a clear barrier to marriage. This explanation is biological since it indicates a particular condition of hindrance to spiritual marriage, which may run in the family and is bad for the couple's unity. Article 133 of the New Civil Code regulates the influence of this viewpoint. Treatment for mental illness is a notion, however treating a person suggests that they are lacking in judgment if they are mentally ill. If a person's mental condition prevents them from engaging in personal, free conduct, it is assumed that they lack judgment. To put it another way, not all mental diseases are seen as obstacles to marriage. The difference between "mental illness" and "lack of mind" in the context of marriage is thus a natural one that applies to mental diseases.

The importance of mood disorders is highlighted by syndromes that manifest as seizures, severely affecting people's lives and regularly or eventually reoccurring between the prisons of seizures and times of well-being. Some mental diseases, which might lead patients to feel clarity and sometimes stagnation for a while, are evaluated in terms of their impact on reasoning ability during other crises. Therefore, having a mental illness does not always entail that a person cannot think.

They are prohibited from being married in any manner under Article 133 of the Civil Code unless a doctor's report is acquired owing to a mental health issue or an unfit negative for their marriage. If a married man or woman is mentally ill, the marriage is regarded to be absolutely null, and as a consequence, the marriage is dissolved, according to the third paragraph of the 145th insanity. The 145th article of the Civil Code was judged to be completely null and the marriage was not dissolved when the pre-marriage mental hospital report was not stated. The circumstance was clearly described. According to Articles 123 and 124 of the General Public Health Law No. 1953 (UHK), marriage is prohibited and delayed if certain health issues develop as a result of the property being exposed to social influences as a result of protection. However, the legitimacy of the marriage cannot be disputed if it is delayed until a later time in accordance with the Public Health Law's recognized health issues. According to the second part of Article 150 of the Civil Code, the conditions can be changed or eliminated after the marriage due to this significant health issue if one of the spouses has any of the aforementioned health issues and if one of the spouses has concealed this serious situation.

Literature Review

The spouse whose condition is determined to be contradictory will be allowed to convey this scenario in a divorce case and will be treated as an absolute nullity in the marriage. Different rules apply to TB; if it persists after 6 months, a second chance may be sought, and if it still persists, marriage is permitted with certain information provided to the prospective spouse. If health issues are at their worst, marriage is not at all permitted. The intended couple may sometimes have to wait until the date set by the court or the legislation. The waiting time for processes like the dissolution of a marriage owing to annulment, divorce, and death has been established by the Civil Code. The lawmaker in this story wants to know whether the divorced lady is expecting at this time. This time starts after the judge's judgment is finalized, unless the judge's ruling on the present marriage is overturned by an annulment or divorce. This time frame for the spouse starts on the day of his passing. Since there are additional reasons for non-coexistence, this 300-day window does not apply in this case. A court order is necessary for both the dissolution of an absent marriage and the

dissolution of an existing marriage. In certain circumstances, the legislator retains the ability to revoke the waiting time with or without a judge's approval.

The law requires women and couples engaged in marriage to produce certain documentation to support their marriage license and to disclose any circumstances that hinder them from getting hitched. These papers include identification cards and medical records proving that none of the individuals have any conditions that would preclude them from getting married. You may acquire the health report from state physicians, health facilities, public and private hospitals, or physicians. The Marriage Exam Regulation with the Decision of the Council of Ministers indicates that if the marriage process health report is obtained, the marriage cannot be consummated. The provincial health directors carry out the health report in accordance with the Ministry of Health's directives. To prevent any neglect and to pay attention to the marriage of the mentally ill, an official health board report is necessary (Marriage Regulation Art. 20/III). A certificate of the prior marriage's dissolution must be presented in addition to the previous marriage's paperwork if one or both of the parties had previously been married. The legal permission document, which must be acquired and signed by the representative, must be attached if either one or both married partners are minors or of legal age.

Annulment of the Previous Court

A court ruling is not requested when rulings like the prior court's annulment are revoked. The marriage officer may examine the civil status of the applicant from the population record if he has any questions about the applications submitted with a court order.

You are required under Article 20 to preserve the following records:

Four copies of the marriage certificate, the identification card with a picture, the medical report, and the document proving the authorized representative's consent.

The parent or guardian must approve to the marriage of a juvenile or a consumer with low resources, and the permission paperwork must be validated by the appropriate authorities. The custody agreement's sided signature is adequate if one of the parents

is deceased or divorced. Marriage Ordinance 20/IV, which is related to how the marriage is conducted, calls for court rulings addressing the designation of a guardian.

For each man and woman whose son was kidnapped within six months and whose son was successfully picked, four legal images are necessary. Hijab is also acceptable, but it must leave the face, chin, and forehead uncovered. The individual is retained in accordance with the population certificate and a circumstance that hinders marriage may seek a marriage certificate if the marriage official has any doubts about the marriage certificate.

Every Turkish citizen must provide an identification card to the marriage officiant, who will take identity registration samples in place of a marriage certificate. A simple identification card cannot be used to consummate a marriage. The marriage officer gets the marriage statement and any accompanying paperwork prepared along with the marriage proposal, and they both go over it to make sure it is filled out properly. The marriage officer determines if the permission of the mother, father, guardian, or the court is available if consent is needed owing to age and takes the appropriate steps to limit it if it is not.

The marriage contract may be executed without the announcement of the intention to wed. The marriage officer evaluates the marital partnership and any supporting documentation in accordance with the Civil Code. It completes any deficiencies that are found by taking the appropriate action. A marriage certificate is provided, at the couple's request, if they are competent, there are no impediments to the union, and all of the necessary paperwork is in order.

The validity of marriage licenses is six months from the date of issuance. The marriage itself must be dissolved if it is legal. If there was no omitted flaw during the marriage, it should not be deemed invalid. If not, you must apply to the marriage official who granted your marriage license within fifteen days to let them know. Rules for marriage issuance are in effect after six months, however this does not always indicate that the marriage is null and invalid.

The marriage's legal requirements are crucial, and the marriage commissioner certifies that the parties to the contract are legally wed. The "prohibition of marriage" is

specifically controlled in the old Civil Code's (prior provisions) articles 100 through 104, as well as in article 103. The new Civil Code, however, eliminated these clauses and stipulated that the marriage rules may only be rejected by the authorized marriage officer after being inspected by him.

Objecting to Marriage

Representatives, divorcés, heirs, property regime contracts, and alimony claimants are among the relevant parties in the objection. These people have the authority to reject the union. According to the Marriage Regulation, the prosecutor, interested parties, and others may object to the marriage and specify how and for how long this objection will be made. The day of the wedding is not the time to raise objections. The new legislation allows for the evaluation of objections up to the wedding day. The objector must have a clear statement, address, and signature if their objection is based on the couple's incapacity to get married or the presence of obstacles to marriage. The public prosecutors may raise an objection up until the marriage is consummated in the event that one of the absolute grounds for nullity is present. If the Public Prosecutor's Office receives a notice of the marriage prohibition, the prosecutor's office will submit any substantial objections to the marriage officer. According to the guidelines and rules outlined in Article 24 of the Marriage Regulation, the marriage officer evaluates the objection. The Office of the Chief Public Prosecutor is notified to proceed if the marriage officiant deems the objection inappropriate. Within ten days, the Office of the Chief Public Prosecutor says that it has filed a case challenging the ban on marriage and that the union will not be consummated. The marriage officiant will refrain from participating in the union's children throughout these 10 days. Without the requirement for an interim injunction from the Public Prosecutor, the marriage officer does not act until the conclusion of the notice period.

If the marriage officer refuses the requirement to wed, everyone who wishes to be married has the option to appeal the judgment under the Turkish Civil Code. In the event that the marriageable person's petitions are denied, this clause still has legal protection. The marriage officer who denies the application has the chance to review and argue their position thanks to the right to object. Applications to the appeals court are filed in order to overturn marriage rulings. The objecting party examines the

objection petition in order to assess the rejection judgment made by the court personnel and the marriage officer. The Family Court, where the marriage officer is based, is the appropriate and authorized court. The appeals court reviews the marriage officer's denial, the objection defense, and any supporting documentation, and it may accept the defense plea. The court ultimately considers the objection and determines the verdict.

The Right to Object to the Rejection of the Marriage Contract

As a result, the protection of minors from marriage refers to the right to protest to the rejection of the marriage contract. The appeals procedure offers a legal review, evaluates the validity of the marriage officer's refusal judgment, and gives a legal check. In Turkey, a marriage officer's decision to deny a request is based on absolute grounds for invalidation, which may result in a contested court ruling. Absolute nullity is defined as the absence of marriage for grounds that threaten public order, and the public prosecutor must be present when the case is filed. The Civil Code does not mention how long the objection to the refusal will last, but it does state that if it is known that there are no prerequisites for marriage, then the marriage cannot be consummated after six months from the day that its regulations have been fired.

Although it is not entirely covered by civil law, the theory does incorporate the idea of non-existence of cohabitation. The term of the marriage will not expire, according to the Turkish Civil Code, if the partners change their gender after being married. But whatever principles the Turkish legal system is built on depends on which court ruling. Additionally, it is indicated that the marriage will dissolve in the event of gender reassignment. A properly formed marriage terminates with a court order in Turkey, according to the legal method that is used when two opposing doctrinal viewpoints are compared, unless there is a death, annulment, divorce, or absence. However, it is incorrect to think that altering how partners reproduce would abolish marriage. Since it is permissible by law, sex reassignment cannot be recognized by the law without a court's approval. As a result, the marriage between two people who are biologically of the same sex but legally of a different sex will continue.

The Turkish Civil Code forbids same-sex unions, and a union between two individuals of the same sex is void even if one of the spouses changes their gender after the union.

Those who desire to be married in a religious or civil ceremony should make their intentions known in front of a designated official. A determination lawsuit is filed without a marriage, unlike an annulment after a marriage. The transaction will be deemed void in an extreme null situation because of its corruption or lack. The Law's Article 145 lists the grounds for an absolute nullity in marriage, including an already-existing union, our persistent lack of judgment, an unwelcome kinship, and mental condition that prevents marriage. Absolute nullity holds that until it ends, a marriage has all of its conditions and repercussions. The ability to bring a lawsuit challenging the nullity of a marriage does not transfer to the heirs; instead, they are limited to pursuing the already-filed complaint. In accordance with Article 130 of the TMK, the person who was previously married must cease his present marriage before being married again, and the person seeking to get married again must demonstrate that his prior marriage has ended. By requiring documentation, this regulation tries to stop people from being married to many people at once. The second spouse in good faith is not protected if the present marriage ends in divorce and the divorce choice is made before the final judgment, and absolute nullity cannot be asserted. Situations that fall under the relative butlan category include momentary loss of judgment during marriage, fault in marriage or people who were married when they were still single, intimidation of marriage, and threats. Only the spouses may file a lawsuit in these relative nullity actions, which call for the revocation of the transfer. The right to an annulment expires six months after the marriage when it is discovered or disappears. Existing marriages will continue to enjoy all the effects of lawful marriages under court annulment decisions.

Conclusion

It is among the most crucial components of family security. The first formal step towards achieving this significant objective is getting married. There are certain conditions that must be followed in order for the institution of marriage to take place, which is very significant. The validity of the marriage is assured as long as these conditions are satisfied. There are some of these principles that permit marriage, and there are some of these requirements that are laws and regulations that forbid marriage. One of the most regular and widely mentioned sorts of invalidity we see today is the invalidation of some issues by defaults, which occurs when certain preconditions are either satisfied or not. A request for the marriage to be declared invalid is part of the Butlan case. The Butlan case is really crucial for maintaining both public peace and individual safety.

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